

Supplementary Table S3. Microbiome composition (16S rRNA) of representative cheese wheels from selected Gouda cheesemake treatments. Raw reads have been uploaded to the NCBI database under Bioproject PRJNA1345744. 16S rRNA sequencing was performed using the Plasmidsaurus 16S rRNA Amplicon & Sequencing Service with Extraction. Sequence analysis was conducted using the EZBiocloud 16S rRNA Gene-Based Microbiome Taxonomic Processing service.

Treatment				16S rRNA sequencing data	
Wheel	Starter	Inoculation Status	Aging Temperature	Accession Number	Valid Reads
A10	Conventional	No	15°C	SRA52817838	8,721
A11	Conventional	No	15°C	SRA52817839	9,407
A12	Conventional	No	15°C	SRA52817840	9,184
B10	Conventional	No	15°C	SRA52817841	5,297
B11	Conventional	No	15°C	SRA52817842	9,258
B12	Conventional	No	15°C	SRA52817843	9,165
C10	Bioprotective	No	15°C	SRA52817844	9,137
C11	Bioprotective	No	15°C	SRA52817845	9,273
C12	Bioprotective	No	15°C	SRA52817846	8,702
D10	Bioprotective	No	15°C	SRA52817847	8,954
D11	Bioprotective	No	15°C	SRA52817848	8,716
D12	Bioprotective	No	15°C	SRA52817849	8,888
E2	Conventional	Yes	4°C	SRA52817826	9,151
E3	Conventional	Yes	4°C	SRA52817827	9,101
E4	Conventional	Yes	4°C	SRA52817828	8,997
E6	Conventional	Yes	10°C	SRA52817832	8,965
E7	Conventional	Yes	10°C	SRA52817833	9,032
E8	Conventional	Yes	10°C	SRA52817834	9,105
E10	Conventional	Yes	15°C	SRA52817850	9,044
E11	Conventional	Yes	15°C	SRA52817851	9,158
E12	Conventional	Yes	15°C	SRA52817852	9,210
F2	Conventional	Yes	4°C	SRA52817829	9,104
F3	Conventional	Yes	4°C	SRA52817830	9,052
F4	Conventional	Yes	4°C	SRA52817831	9,060
F6	Conventional	Yes	10°C	SRA52817835	9,174
F7	Conventional	Yes	10°C	SRA52817836	9,055
F8	Conventional	Yes	10°C	SRA52817837	9,064
F10	Conventional	Yes	15°C	SRA52817853	9,201
F11	Conventional	Yes	15°C	SRA52817854	9,159
F12	Conventional	Yes	15°C	SRA52817855	9,052
G10	Bioprotective	Yes	15°C	SRA52817856	8,987
G11	Bioprotective	Yes	15°C	SRA52817857	9,017
G12	Bioprotective	Yes	15°C	SRA52817858	9,125
H10	Bioprotective	Yes	15°C	SRA52817859	9,144
H11	Bioprotective	Yes	15°C	SRA52817860	9,131
H12	Bioprotective	Yes	15°C	SRA52817861	9,123